

Increasing the Visibility of Creative Practice Research Outputs (NTROs) Literature Review

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Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative

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Glossary

Term	Meaning
citation chaining	The process of using citations and references in relevant articles, books, reports and other grey literature to identify more potential sources for a literature review.
creative practice research outputs	Practice research is 'when practice is the significant method conveyed in a research output' ¹ . Not all creative practice research outputs are submitted for assessment to ERA.
depositing a research output	Adding a copy or representation of a creative practice research output to a repository, in addition to a record containing metadata about the research output.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier ² - a unique persistent identifier for digital objects
ERA	Excellence in Research for Australia
FAIR	A set of guiding principles to make research Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable ³
HASS	Humanities, arts and social sciences
IR	Institutional repository
metadata	Information used to describe an item, which adds meaning and can make the item more findable ⁴
NTRO	Non-traditional research outputs, a term used in the assessment of creative research outputs by ERA. These research outputs are works other than journal articles and monographs. Examples of NTROs include original, live or recorded creative works; curated exhibitions; building designs and websites. ⁵ Not all NTROs are creative practice research outputs (commissioned research reports are also classified as NTROs ⁶).
OA	Open access
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID ⁷
registering a research output	The creation of a record in a repository containing metadata about a creative practice research output, without adding a copy or representation of the research output to the repository.

¹ p3, <https://bl.iro.bl.uk/concern/reports/b51c0f52-9801-49d9-9f00-cca89741091b>

² <https://www.doi.org/>

³ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

⁴ <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/describing-information/metadata>

⁵ p35 – 38, <https://www.arc.gov.au/file/3781/download?token=Wq9o-CbM>

⁶ p39, <https://www.arc.gov.au/file/3781/download?token=Wq9o-CbM>

⁷ <https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/>

1 Introduction

The [Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative](#) (COKI) in collaboration with [Curtin University Library](#) have initiated a project to provide better support for the creative practice research outputs of Faculty of Humanities researchers. The reason for this research is to identify ways to increase the visibility of creative practice research outputs at Curtin University, and document what information (metadata) is important to researchers when describing their creative practice research outputs.

The School of Media, Creative Arts and Social Inquiry (MCASI) in the Faculty of Humanities at Curtin University has been selected as a pilot group for this project, as they are active producers of creative practice research outputs including visual arts and creative writing.

1.1 Research questions

The research questions for this project are:

RQ1: How are MCASI researchers currently disseminating their creative practice research outputs?

RQ2: What are the perceptions of MCASI researchers of registration, dissemination, and deposit of their creative practice research outputs?

RQ3: What are the barriers to registering creative practice research outputs in a repository?

RQ4: What are the barriers to depositing a copy of a creative practice research output in a repository?

RQ5: What metadata is important to describe creative practice research outputs?

This literature review addresses the three research questions in bold: RQ2, RQ3 and RQ4. RQ1 and RQ5 will be explored during interviews with MCASI researchers.

1.2 Structure of this document

The following sections have been included in this literature review:

- Benefits of depositing creative practice research outputs
 - Direct benefits for researchers
 - Indirect benefits for researchers
- Barriers to sharing creative practice research outputs
 - Barriers caused by the nature of creative practice research outputs
 - Barriers caused by systems and workflows
 - Barriers reported by HASS researchers
- Barriers for HASS researchers to open access
- Applying FAIR within HASS
 - Summary of current situation
 - Barriers to the FAIRification of HASS
 - Recommendations to increase FAIRification
- Similar projects underway

1.3 Queries and sources

This research topic spans libraries, archives, digital preservation and the creative arts research community. The queries used for the following sources are listed in Appendix A.

- Library and Information Science Abstracts (LISA) from ProQuest⁸
- Library, Information Science & Technology Abstracts (LISTA) from EBSCO⁹
- Google Scholar
- Google
- Citation chaining

⁸ <https://about.proquest.com/en/products-services/lisa-set-c/>

⁹ <https://www.ebsco.com/products/research-databases/library-information-science-and-technology-abstracts>

2 Benefits of Depositing Creative Practice Research Outputs

2.1 Direct benefits for researchers

- Research outputs will be more discoverable (Burgess, 2019, pp. 1–2; Lambaria, 2020, p. 10)
- Could lead to new opportunities to collaborate with others (Burgess, 2019, pp. 1–2)
- Potentially time-saving as there is research evidence for researchers to consult if needed in the future (Garrett & Gramstadt, 2012, p. 92) e.g. provides link to work online if needed for future funding applications (Shelley, 2020, p. 132)
- Meets funder requirements on open access for funded research (Burgess, 2017, p. 245)
- Saving research outputs in an IR could add gravitas to the research by being associated with the research institution (Lambaria, 2020, p. 11)

2.2 Indirect benefits for researchers

- Research methods can be re-used by others (Burgess, 2019, pp. 1–2)
- Research may have more impact due to being shared more widely (Burgess, 2019, pp. 1–2; Simons & Richardson, 2013, p. 6)
- NTRs evoke discussion and demonstrate creative research (Burgess, 2019, p. 5)
- Research outputs are protected from being lost by preserving them (Burgess, 2017, p. 245)
- Research outputs can be used to support teaching (Garrett & Gramstadt, 2012, p. 94)
- Opportunity to promote the school/faculty via the research outputs (Lambaria, 2020, p. 10)

3 Barriers to Sharing Creative Practice Research Outputs

3.1 Barriers caused by the nature of creative practice research outputs

- Creative practice research outputs are complex – they are ‘tangible, intangible, digital, and physical ... visual arts research data is heterogeneous and infinite, complex and complicated’ (Garrett et al., 2012, p. 31)
 - Complex research outputs containing multiple items – some creative practice research outputs contain multiple items of different types as a project, collection or portfolio, which could be grouped together by using a proposed new item type of ‘project’ (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 15) (see Report 2)
 - Complex metadata – if research output is part of a series, it could require complex linking metadata to represent it in an IR (Meece et al., 2017, p. 215)
 - Complex contributors – who decides to share it where multiple contributors are involved (Lambaria, 2020, p. 12)
- Longer duration of curation needed because research significance can take longer to accrue (Barwick & Toltz, 2017, p. 75)
- Terminology – need to use the language of researchers, rather than library-based language (Garrett et al., 2012, p. 4). For example, the term ‘research data’ was not familiar to some visual artists, and the alternative ‘documenting the research process in the visual arts’ could be used (Garrett et al., 2012, p. 8)
- The research may be physically created outside of the institution so could be less associated by researchers as being a research output (Garrett et al., 2012, p. 13)
- Creative practice research outputs are not automatically tracked for citations like journal articles are (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 54) (see Report 2).
 - A University of Western Australia analysis report suggests minting DOIs for NTROs (Mills & Croker, 2020, p. 27)
 - A UK report on creative practice research in the UK suggests more IRs will be minting DOIs for creative practice research outputs in the future (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 52).
 - Many UK institutions are already using a DataCite tool integrated with their IRs to mint DOIs (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 52)
 - Research outputs in IRs are also important when researchers change institutions, and their previous research outputs are harvested to populate staff profiles and promotion workflows at their new institution (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 51).

3.2 Barriers caused by systems and workflows

- Researchers at Curtin University perform much of the data entry in the current workflow when manually adding creative practice research outputs to Elements¹⁰.
Examples of alternate workflows:
 - University of Sydney has research support staff for data entry and a Research Portfolio Data Acquisitions NTRO team (University of Sydney, 2021, p. 6).
 - University of Queensland have IR deposit forms to match ERA categories, with a help guide so that researchers can self-deposit their NTROs to the IR; they also had funding for a specific project to make these changes for HASS researchers (Marrington, 2019, p. 5,7)

¹⁰ Symplectic Elements, a third-party research management system <https://www.symplectic.co.uk/>

- Laborious to submit creative research outputs for ERA (Prendergast, 2018, pp. 2–3)
- Unappealing repository interface (specific to visual arts researchers) (Meece et al., 2017, p. 213)
- Time-consuming to add creative practice research outputs to IR (Lambaria, 2020, p. 12; Meece et al., 2017, p. 223); as they are more complex to process (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 34) (see Report 2), with some estimating 2-3 times longer to process (Barwick & Toltz, 2017, p. 75). Creative practice research outputs are generally not automatically ‘found’ by research management software like journal articles are found.
- Othering of creative researchers – an IR ‘in which all research in arts is categorized as the research type “Other,” is not successfully providing open access to its scholars, and must address the needs of its arts researchers’ (Meece et al., 2017, p. 228)

3.3 Barriers reported by HASS researchers

- Fear outputs will be re-used without attribution (Lambaria, 2020, pp. 11–12)
- Confusion over what kind of creative outputs can be included in an IR (Gramstadt, 2012, para. 8; Meece et al., 2017, p. 227)
- Concerns about the reproduction quality (Meece et al., 2017, p. 213)
- Concerns about copyright issues (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 55; Lambaria, 2020, p. 12; Meece et al., 2017, p. 216). The fear of infringing copyright preventing researchers and the library from sharing work online, and also causes avoidance of creative project ideas (Aufderheide et al., 2016, pp. 2021–2023). Strategies used to mitigate copyright infringement while sharing creative practice research outputs as open access include:
 - Using extracts of a work rather than the whole work (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 55) (see Report 2)
 - Adding a statement to the IR that provides a method for copyright issues to be reported and subsequent takedown (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 55)
 - Use Creative Commons licenses for the whole creative practice research output, with ‘a notice about the specific content that is copyrighted to the third party within the output’ (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 55)
- Ethics – creative practice research outputs can be ethically more complex as they consist of ‘concepts of ethics acquired through meeting institutional research ethics requirements,’ as well as ‘the notion of ethics that many researchers adopt in their own professional creative practice and the contents of professional codes of conduct’ (MacNeill et al., 2021, p. 74)
- Some researchers do not want their research to be associated with their institution, or marketed by the institution (Garrett et al., 2012, p. 14)
- Perception that others are not interested in their research outputs (Garrett et al., 2012, p. 19)
- Confusion among researchers if a record describes the work created or the uploaded file (Nadim & Randall, 2013, p. 6)
- Fear that research outputs in an IR could be monetised by others (Lambaria, 2020, p. 11)

4 Barriers for HASS Researchers to Open Access¹¹

- Some HASS researchers:
 - Support OA in principle more than practice (Eve, 2014, p. 30)
 - Fear that less restrictive licensing will lead to their original work being remixed and not identifiable (Eve, 2014, p. 32; Narayan & Luca, 2017, p. 5)
 - Are not sure about the meaning of OA
 - Are confused about self-archiving
 - Are less familiar with subject repositories (Creaser et al., 2010, pp. 152–156)
- Lack of engagement with IRs:
 - Researchers are unaware that IRs can be indexed by Google Scholar (Yang & Li, 2015, p. 14)
 - See the IR as low quality (Yang & Li, 2015, p. 14)
 - Have concerns over copyright of items (Cooper et al., 2020, p. 26; Kim, 2010, p. 1917; Serrano-Vicente et al., 2016, p. 16; Yang & Li, 2015, p. 14)
 - Have digital preservation concerns (Kim, 2011, p. 252; Yang & Li, 2015, p. 14)
 - Are not sure how to self-archive (Cooper et al., 2020, p. 26; Kim, 2010, p. 1917; Serrano-Vicente et al., 2016, p. 16; Yang & Li, 2015, p. 14)
 - Feel it takes too long to self-archive (Kim, 2010, p. 1918; Serrano-Vicente et al., 2016, p. 16; Yang & Li, 2015, p. 16);
- Researchers are already sharing their research outputs outside of the IR, including personal websites, academia.edu and ResearchGate (Cooper et al., 2020, p. 25; Narayan & Luca, 2017, p. 5)

¹¹ This section of the literature review has been summarised from Quigley, N. (2021). Engagement with open access among Curtin University Humanities researchers: Exploring the perceptions of, and barriers to open access [Unpublished master's thesis]. Curtin University.

5 Applying FAIR within HASS

5.1 Summary of current situation

- HASS data is different – ‘more fragmented, less data-centric, and in some fields, dealing with physical objects’, and the FAIR principles need to be tailored for the needs of HASS communities (Avanço et al., 2021, p. 22)
- Highlight the benefits of the FAIR principles to HASS researchers to encourage their adoption (Avanço et al., 2021, p. 22)
- Establishing a ‘minimal data set’ will be key to coordinating the ‘actors of the “FAIRification-chain”’: researchers, data stewards, repository managers, librarians, and publishers’ (Avanço et al., 2021, p. 22)
- Need more positive stories of FAIRification from within HASS research communities (Avanço et al., 2021, pp. 22–23)

5.2 Barriers to the FAIRification of HASS

- Awareness of some FAIR concepts are low and sometimes non-existent within HASS research communities, for example ‘persistent identifiers, metadata interoperability standards, and open licenses’ (Avanço et al., 2021, p. 23)
- HASS research is diverse and complex (Avanço et al., 2021, p. 23)
- Some HASS research outputs cannot be made open access due to copyright or privacy reasons, need to educate researchers that outputs can be FAIR without being open (Avanço et al., 2021, p. 23; Mons et al., 2017, p. 51)
- Not enough incentives to adopt FAIR within HASS research communities (Avanço et al., 2021, p. 23)

5.3 Recommendations to increase FAIRification

- The following steps are suggested to be iteratively applied to increase FAIRification in a selected discipline, with new objectives created as required:
 - Define FAIRification with the research community
 - Define the scope of FAIRification (actors and outputs)
 - Identify an objective that all of the stakeholders share
 - Provide training on FAIRification (David et al., 2020, p. 7)
- Consider beginning with an open access mandate at an institutional level (Ernst et al., 2021, p. 22)
- Recruit and activate research data champions (Ernst et al., 2021, p. 22)
- Consider the research needs of all stakeholders by creating research support teams with multiple skillsets e.g. ‘researchers, librarians, software developers’ (Ernst et al., 2021, p. 24)
- HASS researchers know how important their research is, the difficulty is to encourage them to share research outputs more widely (Ernst et al., 2021, p. 24). Suggested communication methods with HASS researchers are storytelling, blogging, infographics and events (Ernst et al., 2021, p. 25)
- Having a unique identifier for each research output such as a DOI is key to making it findable and interoperable (as in FAIR) (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 51) (see Report 2).

6 Similar Projects Underway¹²

The description and storage (or curation and preservation) of research outputs within HASS (humanities, arts and social sciences) is a topic of interest within Australia and internationally, with at least five different organisations working in this area. The five organisations also working on creative practice research description and storage are:

HASS Research Data Commons

HASS Research Data Commons is an Australian government funded 'national HASS and Indigenous digital research infrastructure' which will follow the FAIR data principles (Australian Research Data Commons, 2021). This project is in the planning stages (August 2021).

CAUL

The Council of Australian University Librarians (CAUL) has initiated a project to explore the application of the FAIR principles to 'software and other NTROs (e.g. film, creative writing, website design)' (Council of Australian University Librarians, 2021). The project scope also includes the application of the CARE principles¹³ to NTROs. This project is in the Expression of Interest stage (August 2021).

OPERAS

OPERAS is 'the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area'¹⁴. Their recent report on scholarly communication issues, 'Future of Scholarly Communication: Forging an inclusive and innovative research infrastructure for scholarly communication in Social Sciences and Humanities' includes a chapter on FAIR within the SSH community (Avanço et al., 2021, pp. 22–25).

Their future plans include advocacy for the benefits of FAIR within SSH, 'sharing a minimal metadata set' and creating 'a FAIRification toolkit dedicated to publishing platforms' (Avanço et al., 2021, pp. 22–23). Part of this work will be included in the CO-OPERAS project, 'the OPERAS component addressing the FAIR principles application challenges in the field of Social Sciences and Humanities'¹⁵. CO-OPERAS is an Implementation Network within the GoFAIR initiative, and includes multiple types of research data¹⁶.

Also within OPERAS, the GOTRIPLE platform will be a 'multicultural discovery solution for the social sciences and humanities', and part of the TRIPLE project (Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration)¹⁷.

¹² This section of the literature review has been extracted from Quigley, N. (2021). *Increasing the Visibility of Creative Practice Research Outputs (NTROs): Project Plan* [Unpublished]. Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative.

¹³ <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

¹⁴ <https://www.operas-eu.org/about/>

¹⁵ <https://www.operas-eu.org/international-partnerships/co-operas/>

¹⁶ <https://www.operas-eu.org/international-partnerships/co-operas/>

¹⁷ <https://project.gotriple.eu/gotriple-platform/>

Creative Commons Open GLAM Program

Creative Commons Open GLAM Program¹⁸ supports galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAMs) in making more of their content available as open access.

PRAG-UK

A UK group run by the higher education arts research community with the aim of increasing 'the visibility and accessibility of UK Practice Research and its impact', and making 'this research more searchable internationally'.¹⁹ They are exploring the idea of an Open Library of Practice Research which would host practice research (Bulley & Sahin, 2021, p. 6) (see Report 1).

¹⁸ <https://creativecommons.org/2021/06/10/were-launching-the-cc-open-glam-program/>

¹⁹ <https://prag-uk.org/>

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Appendix A – Literature Review Queries

Query	Database/ source	Number of results
(MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Art") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Humanities") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Fine arts") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Media studies") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Cross cultural studies") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Performing arts education") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Writing") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Literature") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Social research")) AND (MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Open access") OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Information dissemination") OR "open access" OR "repository")	LISA	>100
"non traditional research outputs" or "non-traditional research outputs"	LISA	6
art repositories OR performing art repositories OR creative writing repositories	LISTA	34
"non traditional research outputs" or "non-traditional research outputs"	LISTA	2
humanities arts social science repositories	Google scholar	>100
creative practice research repositories	Google scholar	>100
"creative practice" research sharing	Google scholar	>100
"creative practice" research sharing	Google	>100
non-traditional research outputs	Google scholar	>100